

Thin Layer Chromatography of Metal Ions Complexed with Anils : Part-I

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Three bidentate ketoanils have been found suitable for the detection and separation of metal ions Fe (III), Mn (II), Cu (II), and Zn (II). No spraying agent has been used as the metal-anil complexes are clearly discernible due to their dark colours.

THIN layer chromatography has been sparsely used in inorganic analysis¹⁻⁷ compared to other chromatographic methods. The present communication dealing with the thin layer chromatographic investigation in metal-anil complexes in various solvents, provided a very simple and convenient method for the identification and separation of metal ion mixtures. Three ligands, *p*-iodo, *p*-diethylamino and *p*-dimethylamino anils of 3-phenanthryl glyoxal, abbreviated as A, B and C respectively, have been used for complexation and their structural formulae are as : $\text{RCOCH}=\text{N}-\text{C}_6\text{H}_4-\text{I}$; $\text{RCOCH}=\text{N}-\text{C}_6\text{H}_4-\text{N}(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_2$; $\text{RCOCH}=\text{N}-\text{C}_6\text{H}_4-\text{N}(\text{CH}_3)_2$

(A)
(B)
(C)

where R is phenanthrene nucleus.

Experimental

Silica gel (N. C. L., Poona, India) having been freed from iron and chloride ions and mixed with starch (E. Merck, Garmstadt G. F. R.) as binder (19:1, w/w), was used for coating glass plates. An aqueous slurry was used to prepare the layers of 0.10cm thickness with a

home-built apparatus⁸. The coated plates were dried at 100° for 2-3 hr in an oven. Complex solutions prepared in acetone-dioxane mixture (4:1, v/v) and metal solutions prepared in water from their analytical grade metal halides, were applied with fine capillaries. The R_F values were determined on 25×5cm glass plates.

The plates were developed in glass chambers with ground-in lids by ascending technique.

All the three ligands used, and the metal complexes were prepared and characterised by Upadhyay *et al*⁹⁻¹³.

Results and Discussion

The R_f values of the metal complexes after being complexed with each ligand present in solvent (0.045 gm/100ml) have been found to be not appreciably different (~0.01) from the values reported in Table-1. These results suggest the best resolution of quaternary mixtures of metal complexes with the ligands B and C or of metal ions (complexed on the adsorbent layer with ligand present in solvent) in butanol-acetic acid (4:1, v/v) mixture as well as in butanol.

TABLE 1— R_F VALUES SPOT COLOURS AND λ_{MAX} OF ANIL COMPLEXES

Metal-Anil	Spot colour	λ_{max} (nm)	MeCN	MeOH	EtOH	BuOH	AcOH	BuOH: AcOH (4:1, v/v)	BuOH: AcOH (3:2, v/v)	BuOH: AcOH (2:3, v/v)	BuOH: AcOH (1:4, v/v)
Fe(III)-A	Brown	520	0.32	0.52	0.57	0.20	0.95	0.13	—	—	0.63
Fe(III)-B	Dirty Yellow	640	0.12	0.53	0.80	0.32	—	0.50	0.58	0.62	0.83
Fe(III)-C	Brown	420	0.30	4.73	4.63	0.74	0.82	0.95	0.69	0.74	0.87
Mn(II)-A	Yellow	520	0.33	0.62	0.60	—	—	0.22	0.17	—	0.73
Mn(II)-B	Dirty Yellow	420	0.10	0.84	0.79	0.16	0.83	0.34	0.65	0.64	0.85
Mn(II)-C	Brown	530	0.23	0.77	0.67	0.92	0.73	0.95	0.87	0.86	0.86
Cu(II)-A	Orange	540	0.23	0.62	0.61	0.09	—	—	0.35	—	0.72
Cu(II)-B	Dirty Yellow	400	0.05	0.79	0.79	0.24	0.88	0.14	0.53	0.68	0.85
Cu(II)-C	Yellow	420	0.19	0.70	0.73	0.00	0.72	0.95	0.66	0.76	0.87
Zn(II)-A	Gray	520	0.35	0.61	0.60	0.17	0.94	0.14	—	—	0.74
Zn(II)-B	Dirty Yellow	420	0.06	0.51	0.74	0.25	—	0.23	0.54	0.57	0.82
Zn(II)-C	Brown	585	0.28	0.81	0.73	0.33	0.82	0.95	0.63	0.76	0.30
Development time =			½ h	1½ h	2 h	3 h	3½ h	4½ h	3½ h	3 h	2½ h
Room Temperature =			20°.								

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In the mixture analysis of the metals Fe(III), Mn(II), Cu(II) and Zn(II) the mixture of their very dilute solutions was used and 0.45g constant amount of each ligand (B and C) was added in the solvents. The R_F values of a mixture of the metal-anil products were those of the separate component complexes. In spite of partial overlapping of the coloured spots and trailing (in butanol-acetic acid) the intense colours of the chromatogram components did not obscure their separation and identification.

Abnormally high R_f values obtained in the mixtures than that of acetic acid or butanol may be attributed to the formation of azeotropic mixtures.

Quantitative estimation

It has also been possible to estimate each metal (in mixture) quantitatively by scrapping the chromatogram fragments, eluting the components with acetone and measuring the colours at λ_{\max} of the complex, as given in Table-1. Concentration of the metal was deduced from the standard calibration curve obtained under similar conditions.

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